

EFFECTIVENESS OF FERTILIZERS IN GROWING KRABAS HYBRID CORN FOR GRAIN IN THE CONDITIONS OF POLISSIA, UKRAINE*Klymenko T.,**Stotska S.,**Candidate of Agricultural Sciences**Yurchuk A.,**Rudenko M.,**Khrystyuk M.,**Revutsky R.**applicants of higher education OS master**Polissia National University**Zhytomyr, Ukraine***ABSTRACT**

The article presents the results of scientific research and their proposals on the influence of mineral, organic fertilizers and their combination on the morphological indicators of Krabas hybrid corn. It is recommended to apply organic fertilizer - manure 40 t/ha in combination with mineral fertilizers at the rate of $N_{90}P_{60}K_{90}$, which ensure the yield of corn grain at the level of 76 c/ha.

It was the use of organo-mineral fertilizers that ensured high grain yield, high conditional net profit and the level of profitability when growing Krabas hybrid corn on the farm.

Keywords: corn, hybrid, fertilizers, yield.

Formulation of the problem. Corn is an important, productive, indispensable and profitable crop in the world [3].

In Ukraine, corn plays a major and significant role. Corn is one of the main cereals in the world and in Ukraine, occupies large areas of crops and has large volumes of grain production. The average corn yield in Ukraine reaches 70 c/ha [6].

But paying attention to the rather large yield potential of good corn hybrids and the average yield in Ukraine, it can be analyzed that there is still a small realization of the potential of corn yield [7].

Modern intensive technologies are one of the methods of increasing corn yield, as well as the use of various microfertilizers, which contain all the important macro-micro elements that the plant needs so much during certain growing periods of growth and development [2].

Analysis of recent research and publications. Farmers around the world are interested in the economic benefits of harvesting corn, so the creation of technologies to obtain a crop of corn for grain of good quality with positive characteristics is so relevant that agricultural producers create all the necessary conditions and provide many scientific recommendations that are interesting and promising [4, 10].

Climatic changes are occurring quite actively, affecting the temperature indicators of air, soil, the amount of precipitation, which are sometimes excessive or simply not enough, and many different new pests and diseases quickly appear [1].

Increasing the yield of agricultural crops is possible under the conditions of a correctly selected hybrid (variety) and fertilizer to nourish plants with appropriate elements and increase soil fertility. Currently developed crop growing technologies allow obtaining a high level of yield of good quality products. However, it is

also necessary to take into account the economic component that affects the profitability of crop production [5, 9].

One of the main factors in increasing corn yields is the use of fertilizers, which allows for a significant increase in productivity and improvement in product quality [8].

The purpose of research. To establish the yield of Krabas hybrid corn and the qualitative characteristics of the grain depending on the use of mineral and organo-mineral fertilizers.

The research was conducted on the farm of Korosten district of Zhytomyr region, which is located in the Polissya zone of Ukraine.

The research was carried out on light gray and sod-podzolic soils of the northern zone of Zhytomyr region and are favorable for agriculture and growing various crops.

In our research, the Krabas corn hybrid was used.

The Krabas hybrid is a mid-season, intensive type recommended for cultivation in such climatic zones as Polissya, Forest-steppe and Steppe.

A very good hybrid in terms of yield, but for this it is necessary to create all the conditions and adhere to all growing technologies. The grain of the hybrid has a toothed type. Resistant to diseases such as blister blight and helminthiasis. FAO of the Krabas hybrid is 300. Grains in a row are 37-40 pieces. The weight of 1000 grains of the hybrid reaches 345-350 grams. The plants are 310-320 centimeters high. The height of the cob attachment is 100-130 centimeters.

Research results. We analyzed the results of research on the cultivation of Krabas hybrid corn during 2023-2024. According to the research results, the morphological indicators of corn were influenced by the use of mineral and organic fertilizers and their applications, which had a positive effect on yield (table 1).

Table 1

Plant morphology of Krabas hybrid corn, average for 2023-2024

Research options	Plant height, cm	Head attachment, cm	Planting in bales before harvesting
1. Without fertilizer (control)	205	92	8
2. N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₉₀	231	119	8
3. Manure 40 t/ha + N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₉₀	250	123	8
NIR _{0,5} cm	24,3		

In the variant where fertilizers were not applied (control, variant 1), the height of the plants reached 205 centimeters. When applying only mineral fertilizers at the rate of N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 2), the height increased to 231 cm, and when applying organo-mineral fertilizers - manure 40 t/ha + N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 3) increased the height to 250 centimeters.

Compared to the variant without fertilizers (control), the application of mineral fertilizers increased the height of the plants by 28 cm, and when applying organo-mineral fertilizers by 45 cm, which is a significant difference for the NIR_{0,5} - 24.3 centimeters.

It was found that in the variant without fertilizers (control, variant 1) the attachment of the ear was recorded at a height of 92 centimeters, with the application of mineral fertilizers N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 2) - 119 cm, and with manure 40 t/ha + N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 3) - 123 centimeters. This significantly affects the quality of harvesting.

It should be noted that the height of the plants and the height of attachment of the ear on the stem did not affect the lodging of the plants. In all variants of the research, the degree of lodging was within 8 points.

The use of mineral fertilizers and their combination with organic fertilizers affected the development of corn plants (table 2).

The number of plants before harvesting in the control variant (without fertilizers, variant 1) reached 64 thousand plants per hectare. With the application of mineral fertilizers N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (option 2), the density increased to 70 thousand plants per hectare.

In crops, the largest number of plants was observed in the option with the application of manure 40 t/ha + N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (option 3) - 73 thousand plants per hectare, which had a positive effect on the formation of the corn crop.

Table 2

Total number of Krabas hybrid corn plants and leaves, average for 2023-2024

Research options	Density before harvest, thousand pcs./ha	Number of leaves on a plant, pieces	Leaf surface, thousand m ² /ha
1. Without fertilizer (control)	64	12	39,8
2. N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₉₀	70	15	47,5
3. Manure 40 t/ha + N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₉₀	73	16	48,6
NIR _{0,5} thousand pcs./ha, thousand m ² /ha	3,0		1,7

Fertilizer application contributed to an increase in the number of leaves on the plant. Their greater number was observed in the variants where fertilizers were applied (variants 2 and 3) - with the use of mineral fertilizers - 15 pieces and organo-mineral fertilizer - 16 pieces compared to the control - 12 pieces.

The number of leaves per plant determined the total area of the leaf surface in crops.

In the variant without fertilizers (control, variant 1), the leaf area reached 39.8 thousand m²/ha, with the use of mineral fertilizers N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 2) it increased to 47.5 thousand m²/ha, and with manure 40 t/ha + N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ - to 48.3 thousand m²/ha, which was positively reflected in the yield of corn grain.

Studies indicate that corn yield was positively affected by the application of organic and mineral fertilizers. The data are presented in (table 3).

Table 3

Yield of Krabas hybrid corn, average for 2023-2024

Research options	Corn yield, c/ha	Yield increase	
		c/ha	%
1. Without fertilizer (control)	41	-	-
2. N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₉₀	59	18	143
3. Manure 40 t/ha + N ₉₀ P ₆₀ K ₉₀	76	35	185
NIR _{0,5} , c/ha	23,6		

When growing Krabas hybrid corn, the grain yield was obtained in the variant without fertilizers (control, variant 1) at the level of 41 c/ha. The use of fertilizers significantly increased the yield. With the application of mineral fertilizers N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 2), the grain yield increased to 59 c/ha, and with the application of

manure 40 t/ha + N₉₀P₆₀K₉₀ (variant 3) - to 76 c/ha. The yield increase was obtained, respectively, 18 c/ha and 35 c/ha compared to the control (without fertilizers) and is significant for the NIR_{0,5}- 23.6 c/ha.

Conclusions. When growing the Krabas corn hybrid on a farm, it is recommended to apply organic fertilizer - manure at a rate of 40 t/ha in combination with mineral fertilizers $N_{90}P_{60}K_{90}$, which ensures grain yield at the level of 76 c/ha.

References

1. Vozniuk N., Skyba V., Likho O., Sobko Z., Klymenko T. (2023). Forecasting the adaptability of heat-loving crops to climate change in Ukraine *Scientific Horizons*, 26 (2), 87-102.
2. Organic fertilizers: a teaching aid. Zhuravel S. V. and others. / Edited by S. V. Zhuravlya. Zhytomyr: Publishing House of the Polesie University, 2020. 200 p.
3. Kravchuk, N. N., Kropyvnytskyi, R. B., Zhuravel, S. V., Klymenko, T. V., & Trembitska, O. I. (2021). Soil-protective technologies as an important component of agricultural biologization in the conditions of the Central Polissia of Ukraine. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 254, Archive number 05012. doi:10.1051/e3sconf/202125405012.
4. Klymenko T.V. Monitoring the climate situation in the Polissya zone of Ukraine / T.V. Klymenko// *Sciences of Europe (Prague, Czech Republic)* No. 75 2021. – P. 14-17.
5. Gavrilyuk V. M., Blaschuk M. I., Semerun T. B. Which hybrid to choose. Proposal. 2018. No. 2. P. 72–73.
6. Belov Ya.V. Directions for optimizing corn growing technologies under climate change conditions. *Bulletin of the Black Sea Region Agricultural Science. Mykolaiv*, 2018. No. 4. P.74-81.
7. Prysyzhnyuk L. M., Shovgun O. O., Korol L. V. (2016). Assessment of stability and plasticity indicators of new corn hybrids (*Zea mays* L.) in the conditions of Polissya and the Steppe of Ukraine. Variety study and protection of plant variety rights. Pp. 16-21.
8. Gospodarenko G. M. (2015). Fertilizer application system: manual. Kyiv: LLC "SIC GROUP Ukraine". 332 p.
9. Polishchuk, V., Klymenko, T., Stotska, S., & Pototska, S. (2025). Soil microbiological activity in winter rye crops under different fertilisation systems and biopreparations. *Scientific Horizons*, 28(10), 77-84. doi: 10.48077/scihor10.2025.77
10. Stotska S. V., Didora V. G., Klymenko T. V., Kotkova T. M. The influence of elements of growing technology on corn grain productivity. *Tavria Scientific Bulletin*, 2025. No. 142. Part 2. Pp. 126–132.